

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello. Thank you so much for agreeing to take part in this interview. My name is Anna Makarudze and I am pursuing a Masters in Software Engineering at the Blicking Institute of Technology. I'm investigating how developers in Mendean has perceived vulnerabilities in free open source software or open source software dependencies they include in their projects. This is based on how supply chain attacks have become very common and they are being mostly launched through dependencies.

And I'm focusing on five web frameworks, Django, Next.js, Spring Boot, Laravel, and Ruby on Rails. Then participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time. You can skip questions which you are not comfortable answering. And I will not retain any personal data or identifiable information. Will not share your name, your role, e-mail address, or any identifiable details. And will not publish them or share them with anyone. Your responses will remain anonymous and do not be linked to the project that you represent. And the interviews will be kept in the duration of the study to allow the supervisors to verify the authenticity of the reported data, after which they will be deleted. And we also conform to GDPR.

So before we start, maybe you could start by introducing yourself. whether you tell us which web framework you're using of the file. Then you can tell us whether you're a developer using the framework or are you a contributor or a maintainer with that framework? And also how many years of experience you have using that framework and how many years of experience you have as a developer.

Yes.

Speaker 2

Okay. Yeah. Okay. Thank you for like, for the briefly introduction. Yeah, just to, I'm quick about myself. Like I'm a senior developer and like I have been senior developer for like, I

mean, I have been a software engineer for like over five years already, I mean like three to five years of that.

And like mostly I am the full stack developer. So like I have to a full stack web developer. So I have to work on both like front end and the back end side, especially the framework of the Next.JS that you mentioned one of the list there. Yeah, for the Next.JS itself, I have been using it for like three years already. It was started by when when it come to the project that like we use React, I still remember it is a project of like the educational website that we just want to make a website for linguistic learning, especially English. And then like we have to handle the multiple stage in that learning ecosystem. For example, if you still didn't get into the website, They have to go to login and then some students may stuck in the first lesson or some may almost finish the first lesson, but they pause and they drop off and when they get back again, they have to go into that one. So we noticed that it is so much complex stage management that we have to handle and react alone.

It's not that enough. So we designed it to go beyond just the React library. So we're looking for some kind of the framework that we can, especially we have, we have people, the team of three to four engineer. And because like, the naked itself, like it has, is more convenient for you to handle on deployment and stuff, especially they have the as the native cloud deployment. as well as like the team complexity. Like it can reduce the team complexity as well because it's framework. So like the main difference between library framework is like, you know, when you use rivalry, it depends on you to set the rules to use library. So like if you have a strong rule, that's totally fine. But like when it comes to like, you know, the multiple like complex session, like our use cases, we cannot set the rule on that. So we just want to use some kind of the like industry proven framework, which why I use like Next.js back then for the projecting. And then, yeah, and I love it since then for the Next.js, I think. Yeah, that's the quick introduction.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. Okay, so when you use Next.js for your projects, Do you combine it with projects from other ecosystems like Python or Java or PHP or Ruby or you just use next JS and JavaScript libraries on?

Speaker 2

Yeah, yeah, that's really good. Like for the for the flood inside we use the. That's a good question. I mean, like for the most, mostly we compile with the native JavaScript with, bundler and stuff then, and then we can compile to static side. But when the project grows up, of course, like somehow just the JavaScript ecosystem is enough. So like I still

remember that the time that we use kind of the type checking, because back then, I mean, even now, like TypeScript doesn't have type.

So like we just want to, you know, doing some kind of the type checking and then like we, I think it's similar to Python. Python have some library that can do the native type checking, but back end of that is Rust. It's kind of the type checking, binding with TypeScript and behind the scene of that is like six or something beyond.

Yeah, but like mostly on the on the static site generation, we use the JavaScript. And then and they like for the other part, it may be other languages like Python or stuff. But but they they communicate with each other by just HTTP things. So I'm not sure it's that relevant to your question. Yeah.

Speaker 1

All right. And then suppose the security issues or vulnerabilities discovered in your project. How are the reports managed?

Speaker 2

Yeah, yeah, the security is 2 things. Yeah, right. Yeah, yeah, that's that's a good question, you know. I'm like when we were working with the web. I'm like we back then we thought that like the security thing will come only from the web. Example, like, you know, like cross site forgery, like SQL injection and stuff. And then, we, I mean, like Next.js or even like in our backend side backend, we use like Next or Python, like, the other framework, they're likely to have some kind of prevention of those like security list or vulnerability from the web aspect. But like what we did then, and it's like, it was like totally surprised me is that the vulnerability, it could come from our like, you know, our like installation or our dependency as well. Like, you know, when you use like Next.js, behind the scene of Next.js, it's like, it's like no package management system, it's not JS itself. Or you use something else that's okay, but like the package management of JavaScript ecosystem, like, you know, is do some kind of the magic behind the scene. First of all, like if you install Next.js, for example, it will pull like number of the dependency pushing in the node module and then you have no idea what's going on then. And I still remember like some kind of the supply chain security like CVE something that if I if we install that dependency and then like it will pull that like that vulnerable vulnerable library into our project and it can leak our credit and shield and stuff. So like that's the first time that like it's It may it may at like change change the perception of the security that it can not only come from the application interface, but it can come from the development phase or like, dependency that injected when you install them as well. Yeah, and like we, and yeah, we, after we know that, like we just try to, like, to be honest, at first, like we didn't read the release notes that

much. Like, you know, when we just install, I mean, we leave the release notes or the note or document of the library that we use, but like we don't trace it back to the, you know, the, how to say, like the inbound of that library.

For example, like Next.js may use call.js, which is like, is hidden somewhere. Back then, we didn't care about that. We even don't read the document of it. But after that, we realized, oh, no, we can let those Next.js can pull some kind of vulnerable library.

We have to not only investigate the library itself, but trying to understand which library of such library that we use will pull in and then trying to mitigate the risk back then there. Yeah, I think that's what we did. Trying to read more and then, yeah, yeah, that's just, yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you for that. And then my next question is, you've already mentioned that you are aware of how, you know, you can pull a vulnerable dependence within your dependency because of one dependency that you installed and they chooses other dependencies.

My next question is, are you aware that the dependency you are using in your projects can actually expose you to supply chain attacks where the vulnerabilities in that dependency can launch, can be used to launch an attack on your system? And then if you are using me, if other people are using your dependencies as well, It can actually be also attacked through that dependency.

Speaker 2

Yeah, like back then, like, honestly, we didn't know that one. Yeah. I mean, I mean, like, it's not, I think, I think like currently, like people, like there are people and I think like it's a big group of people who don't know that one, especially like, you know, back then we wrote a code by ourselves. So like if something break, we know how it's break and why it's break and then we can read things.

But right now people will write a code, you know, like by the AI and I can write the code for you and then it can finish the thing for you. But like if you don't care the output of the AI code, you don't investigate it, that it's done. And I feel like, I mean like I'm not yet facing that situation, but like,

I just saw the code of the junior engineer, not from my company, but from I knew him. And he just write a code and he just like share some kind of the level level system programming code. Like it's not JavaScript, but it's like, you know, the C or something like Rust, something like that one.

And they like they use an AI and then AI use like, you know, wrote the Rust for him. And then in the Rust code, like it use unsafe, which is like, you know, it can break the memory, like vulnerability and stuff. And they like that person like didn't aware of it anyway.

So like, and she just deployed it as well. And then like some of the user even like not that much, like one or two people use that application. without knowing that, okay, that is vulnerable code written from the AI and then we don't know it yet.

So I think that may similar to what you just said that like, yeah, we still don't know, like especially the supply, I don't know how to call like supply chain dependency vulnerability kind of thing. Yeah.

And also like when we're talking about the vulnerability or security, we often like rely on a third party scanner. For example, in the web, you would like, you know, rely on the OLAP and then the OLAP has a tool, or you would rely on a third party company that can scan a thing for you. And in those like third party company, like if they're done, and I guess that like somehow they don't like care about like, you know, you know, like supply chain of the dependency, it can break.

I was curating as well. So Yeah. And like the complete, I mean, the working tools that we have in the market right now, they how to say, they just focus on the current situation. What it means is like, if you let user interact with this, okay, what vulnerability our security list could be regarding those interfaces. But like those working tool doesn't care that much for, you know, the dependency of your installation would would draw something good or bad.

That's it. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you for that. Oh, the next question I want to ask you. So do you identify vulnerable dependencies within your project? What tools do you use? For example, to scan.

Speaker 2

Yeah, like because mostly I work with the web. So yeah, like OLAP scanning. I mean, the OLAP is kind of the, not the tools, but OLAP has tools as well. So like we, but like OLAP is like kind of the document information and okay, you have to aware to do this. And then yeah, we like basically we just use data tool to scan vulnerability on our web as well. This is the first thing that we do. And like, if you use some like, if you use some observability tools, observability tools like, how to say, I forgot the name of it. Probably like Kibana or something that you can like, you know, if I, I mean, okay, let me explain how it works first. I

probably like remind the name of it. It's work like this one. So like you, you land the application and then this tool will try to watch your application behind the scene.

And if something break, I mean like, you know, the request came in and then it's break or like, you know, someone like click on that UI and then it's break the whole thing. These two will capture those breaking, breaking event. And then like you can trace.

to to the like you know the memory at this not that memory memory was like trace to like you know the at the time capture like um um which is the value of each variable regarding the area of the the the area and stuff and we use that one to to to I mean they have some kind of the security scanner as well and then we use that for our scanning things yeah um.

Speaker 1

GitHub is a tool, Dependabot, which you can use in your CI/CD process. And also it is GitHub security advisories. Do you happen to use those tools as well in your project?

Speaker 2

Oh, yeah, yeah. Right now we are using Dependabot, but mostly it's for is for dependency upgrading automation. So like if you want to, I mean, just dependable, it's just for like you watch your dependency, then it's upgraded automatically. And yeah, like, and we don't have the protocol for that one. So like if Dependabot just open the pull request and then like if people just came in, okay, that's totally fine. It's just approve an edge merge into the thing and stuff. I think that's for the CI part.

Oh, yeah. And like, we use cloud as all like aws thing. And in aws, like, you know, we have some kind of the tool scanner, even though, like like most of the time. even the senior engineer or the engineer, we don't care that much for, you know, for the alert from the aws security scanner. But yeah, there are.

Speaker 1

Oh.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

Oh, so it's so you said you said you don't care much about this. Alert from so you OK, so you might get an alert and not actually it's where even you get it tells you that there's some risk with your dependency.

Speaker 2

Yeah, yeah. Let me let me clarify this one. So I feel I think like it's not just like we don't care, we care, but like, you know, somehow this scanner just throw the repetitive alert to us. So it's like, yeah, it's like, yeah, this is risk, this is risk, this is risk. And then we just investigate, investigated it. And then, okay, there's no risk at all, but it's just throw the risk. Or somehow, if your system is like so legacy, it's like it's too old, even though we know that that is the security issue, and the AWS or even like, or regarded of like any tools that alert security thing for us. Like we cannot do anything. I mean like because people don't want to touch the code because if you want to touch the code and it can break and if you break, I mean like, you know, we cannot compromise with just, you know, like unknown security proven things, I guess. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Oh, okay. So in other words, you will update dependencies if they don't introduce breaking changes to to your code. But if they are breaking changes to your code, especially in Vegas code, you would rather keep using those dependent dependencies with vulnerabilities than update the code.

Speaker 2

I'm sorry. So like your question is like, I I'm I'm okay.

Speaker 1

My question is, what factors influences the decision to update to new versions of the dependencies within your projects. You have mentioned that for old code, you would rather not touch it, even if you get alerts for dependencies that have security issues. So that you my question is your decision to update dependencies, does it that it does it depend on whether the Changes being introduced with the new version Do not have breaking changes for you to update the code.

Speaker 2

Yeah. Yeah, that's also funny. Like, you know, like, I can share this one. Like, there was a time that, like, okay, there is some kind of security alert in our code. And then, okay, we try to resolve it as well. It doesn't like, okay, we don't care at all, but most of the time we don't, but I mean like can like 80/20 thing because like 80% it is limitative task. But like there was some kind of the security issue of the like, you know, in the JavaScript ecosystem that you like upgraded to and then can lead your own cadence sharing application. And at first, we didn't care about-- I mean, we did care, but we didn't land it as a top priority, even though

the risk of that issue is quite dangerous. But we didn't have time to investigate it more in detail. But one of the team just go into the social media, read the Facebook, and then, OK, people are talking so much about this thing. And that's that is the time that we just get back to our code. And it's okay.

We have to do it right now, because right now, people surrounding us like facing the same thing. I think that's just the the big, big, like the biggest like moment that I know that. Okay, it have to be something break first, and that people try to, you know, upgrade and stuff.

Yeah alright.

Speaker 1

So next the key is is in the JavaScript ecosystem. And there are many libraries on NPM which are no longer being maintained, more or less like abandoned. So how do you check the maintenance of dependencies in your project to know that this dependence we are still using, is it being maintained or it's no longer being maintained? So whatever vulnerabilities in that dependence are going to, are never going to be at risk.

Speaker 2

Yeah. Yeah, right. I feel like for the, I mean, like, it's not that direct factor that we check for them. I mean, like, we check it, but like, mostly we prefer to use any dependency that bigger company than us use or like enterprise gated use it, for example. So like, you know, for example, I still remember that like we chose some kind of the like JSON serializer or something, which is really big. It's old, but like, you know, the enterprise or our client use it. That's why we use it. And like, regardless of like, you know, like, regardless of this, I mean, I don't know. I mean, like, we cannot guarantee that even though it's old and it's enterprise gate, it doesn't mean that it's, it has no, you know, vulnerability, right? But because it's enterprise grade and in a bigger company and everyone use it, that's why we use it. But okay, I mean, nowadays we Because right now I contribute to open source and things like I may know that how to notice the pattern of the maintainable and like unmaintained library. So we often see, we often see the commit history in the library and then we can just inform that as well. Like what is, what was the last time that the library got updated or like which part of the driver is got updated. So sometimes it's like, you know, it's updated every day, but it's just like the read me. They're trying to push it. Okay, this duplicate duplicate. So it's not a good thing. And yeah, like, you know, and yeah, like and and like normally we we just like Google it or right now we just, you know, like I am it that. Okay, is this secure to use in our project and things like that one. We don't go that we don't we don't we don't go any any like further in the process to investigate it.

00:25:07 Speaker 1

Thank you. My next question is, suppose we have a dependency that is vulnerable and CVE has already been publicized, that there's this vulnerability and it's risky is high. At the same time, that's how do you address that in your project? Do you, how do you, how do you address it in the project? Do you upgrade it or do you remove it? Sometimes a vulnerable dependency might not have maybe another vulnerable, it may be an update to upgrade to.

Speaker 2

Wow. If that's like dependency is like quite all, where do I get it? We drop it. We drop it, yeah. We drop it that dependency. Because to upgrade it, if it's a too old, like you come with breaking change, a lot of breaking change. So like we just try to backward it back until we find it like, you know, the old thing. And yeah, but it suffer like honestly. But for quite the new things, like new library, if it is in our core, I mean, in our core application, we try to upgrade it. But if it is like, you know, it's just like, it's not in our core, or it have like several alternative. For example, like in the JSON serializer, you have like, you know, 10 or 20 alternative in JavaScript ecosystem.

We, if we can, and it have like less effect toward our code base, we just try to remove it out and then use like more enterprise gate on that one.

Speaker 1

Thank you. Suppose how long does it take for you to resolve to update binary dependencies within your projects from the time that you get a security alert to the time that you resolve it. Normally.

Speaker 2

Yeah, if if that is like like, like, if it is in our core system and And it's it's proven that that is the empirical evidence. Okay, this is like totally security. We can do it in a day or two. I mean, like, you know, I mean, we do like this. We just trying to like backward, like down get the system first. Is that what we can just drag getting into what the version that doesn't use that one or like. That's probably one or two days just for navigating. I mean, like just for navigating, it's like half a day. That's totally fine. But if we just have to upgrade it, that could take like over three days to a week. That depends on the size of the project, the size of the library, and the impact of such library will be in our code base. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And then how do you handle vulnerable dependencies that are no longer being maintained?

Speaker 2

Yeah. You mean in the context of that, like, we know that it's no longer maintained, right? And it's vulnerability. Yeah. I think we did the same. I think like we just try to upgrade it. If it's small or it's too old, we just try to downgrade it. Or like, but like if it unmaintained as well, we're just trying to, I mean, we will say, I mean, we just downgrade first to the version as okay, it's no vulnerability. And then we'll set someone to do some kind of the research of the alternative regarding that like library.

Speaker 1

Thank you. So for dependence within your ecosystem, sometimes taking over abandoned projects, which you have expanded this in heavily rely on may be a consideration. I've seen this happen in the Django ecosystem. If people see that they really use a library and they need it, sometimes they step up to maintain it. So is this something that happens within the JavaScript ecosystem or after a dependency is no longer being maintained, we just switch to an alternative.

Speaker 2

Yeah. Yeah, this is this is a good question. I think like in in here in in my area like people, especially like including my team, like we prefer to switch to, you know, another library or switches to like the like any available library alternative that we have because it's more convenient.

And that's the thing that we noticed that. But like, that's funny because like my friend, we are talking about the JavaScript library, okay? But like there are a few people that's just like, you know, oh, hey, this is the vulnerability and they want to step up and try to resolve that problem as well. But I feel like delay show is quite like small. I mean, most of the team here just want to switch it to the alternative. We call it more convenient.

Speaker 1

All right. Thank you. My next question is, what practices and tools are in place for supply chain mitigation? So supply chain attacks mitigation for your projects. Do you have a structure or a security team to handle them or Just general things is the okay?

Speaker 2

Yeah, I'm like, I work in several sides of the organization, like in the bigger organization, like enterprise grade, like we have the dedicated, I mean, the dedicated team toward the security thing and then like they will do some kind of the automation to prevent the security and then they have some kind of the offending team that investigate the problem in depth

as well. This is for the bigger company, but for my current company, it's not that big. So like it's kind of small to medium size. We don't have the dedicated team. So we just trying to read the news and the report and even like, you know, the article of the big tech company and then they was trying to know that, okay, is that Lala went to our code base identification or not. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Alright. If any of the projects you have worked on ever been exposed to supply chain attack.

Speaker 2

In my previous projects.

Speaker 1

Yes.

Speaker 2

I think no directly. No. Yeah, but like indirectly there is some kind of the like JavaScript thing that's it's like making change like big, big, big change like two years ago. That's it. We got affected as well. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And then what factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

What aspect?

Speaker 1

What factor?

Speaker 2

Oh, okay.

Speaker 1

Help you to identify.

Speaker 2

Yeah, right? Yeah. The alert system from aws. Of course, I mean like, if they, if they alert something repetitive and we will investigate it. But and then it is like, we identify if that's

like worth it to to go deep down to investigate it more. That's the first thing. The second thing is just like, you know, people will tell you, I mean, people will tell you in the social media in the web board and things like that one. There's another factor as well. And yeah, and I'm one of the team. I mean, like in our team, like if our team like found something, even like, like, you know, Not only about the working, but like from the web board or from the books or from their reading and the community they will share in the team as well. And that's another factor that we will, we will count into to investigate it. And then like we will, we'll assign someone as the like, you know, the research to do the research on that security thing and stuff. And then let, let design it should be removed or upgrade or downgrade things. Yeah.

00:34:21 Speaker 1

All right. And what challenges do you face which hinder you in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, I feel like because we don't have the specialist in the team regarding the security skills. So it's quite challenging, even though we have a lot of tools right now, but people that cannot interpret the results of the tools. That is nothing at all, right? So yeah, I think that's the first challenging thing. So like, and if we want to assign someone to do research, that's mean that we lost someone to do our work as well.

So like it's kind of the balancing between worthiness and like, you know, the vulnerability that we are track of it. So the first is like, yeah, the capacity of a team. The second is like the time that we have to spend on that one. I think. I think that's that's that's all I can think of it now.

00:35:27 Speaker 1

Alright, thank you. And what recommendations do you have for dependency management to mitigate supply chain attacks?

00:35:42 Speaker 2

Yeah. Okay, even answer it as the company, it would say that, just use the enterprise-grade library. So, if enterprise use it, if they have some kind of enterprise support, if they have some kind of the social, I mean, not like the company support, like just do this. I think that's why, like, people prefer to buy the enterprise-grade open source, even though they have the community-grade open source, because in the enterprise game, you can talk with someone if vulnerabilities occur.

So that's the first thing. Yeah, for as of the company that I answer, but like as an engineer and and right now, I will say that like like you should just go deep down a bit into the library that you are going to use. For example, if I use next JS right now, I won't. I mean, that depends on the use case as well.

I mean, like, if we are you if we are working with like kind of sensitive data like finance or health or anything that can leak the data, we have to like be careful and go into to the rivalry itself and like trying to understand like which dependency of such rivalry use as well.

But it's not that easy to be honest. Like it's require a lot of these skills, times and Yeah, it's like. Yeah, you have to balance this. That's it.

Speaker 1

Yeah. Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

Okay. Okay, that's that's all from from our side.

Speaker 1

Yes, that's all. Thank you. I really like taking your time to participate.

Speaker 2

Okay, cool. Thank you. Alright.